

THE PERIOD AHEAD OF US WILL BE A PERIOD OF GREAT CHANGES FOR UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article describes in detail the initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, during his speech at the inauguration ceremony.

On July 14 of this year, the inauguration ceremony of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who won the early election, was held in the magnificent meeting hall of the Senate. In the election, our people voted the most for the candidate of Shavkat Mirziyoyev - 87.05 percent.

At the heart of this great confidence of the Uzbeks, of course, is the real truth that in recent years, in the framework of the Strategy of Actions and the Strategy of Development, the great and noble work of the National Leader to build a new Uzbekistan and lay the foundations of the Third Renaissance has taken a firm place in the hearts of our people.

On May 8, 2023, in the first week of the adoption of our new Constitution, the head of state signed the decree “On the appointment of early elections of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. This is a clear indication that the President has personally started to follow the new Constitution of Uzbekistan.

Because, according to the third paragraph of Article 128 of the Constitution, “The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has the right to appoint the election of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan before the deadline”.

Also, in Article 108 of the New version of our Constitution, the norm related to taking the oath at the meeting of the Oliy Majlis for the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to take office after the election has been strengthened.

In world experience, such a ceremony is called “Inauguration”. The essence of this term, in simple words, is to take an oath and enter one’s position.

Inauguration, according to the state practice of European countries, is a solemn ceremony of the head of state taking office. Historically, the tradition of coronation of the King was at the center of this ceremony, and later this custom was preserved only in Great Britain.

Nowadays, in most developed countries, the inauguration is held in the style of a

modern official constitutional ceremony, without pompous celebrations.

For example, in accordance with the US Constitution, the newly elected President of the United States of America takes the oath of office in a traditional open ceremony in front of the Capitol building in Washington.

The American style of inauguration has been adopted by many countries of the world. At the same time, in the USA, the inauguration was always held on March 4, but in 1933, in connection with the introduction of the 20th amendment to the US Constitution, the date of this solemn ceremony was moved to January 20.

In a number of other countries, the inauguration will be held on a specific date. In particular, it is stipulated in the legislation that this ceremony will be held in Mexico on December 1, in Brazil on January 1, in Colombia on August 7, and in Germany on July 1.

In most countries of the world, the date of the inauguration has not been determined. Our national practice in this regard shows that Uzbekistan belongs to the next group of countries. In other words, our legislation does not specify the exact date on which the inauguration will be held.

“Inauguration” is Latin word, and its dictionary meaning is “to make a good intention by looking at the flight of a bird”.

It seems that the basic meaning of this word, the pronunciation of which is so difficult that it “breaks” the tongue, is not alien to us. On the contrary, very close, very dear.

First of all, the meaning of this word contains the characteristic virtue of our people - the way to do good intentions. Intention is a desire, purpose, desire, hope.

Everything depends on intention. Intention is the foundation of actions. As mentioned in the hadith, “Certainly, actions depend on intentions. Indeed, everyone has what he intends”.

Most of those present at the solemn event - deputies and senators - tested one simple truth on the example of their fate. Even so, it is true that today’s voter is not yesterday’s voter.

The demands of today’s voters are strict, their goals are clear, and their dreams are high.

Today’s voter wants to live a happy, full and prosperous life today, not tomorrow.

Today’s voter expects a clear election program from the candidate he will vote for. He carefully studies the presented program, carefully and critically analyzes it.

In this sense, the fact that an absolute majority of voters voted for Shavkat Mirziyoyev is closely related to the following three important factors.

The first factor: the majority of today’s voters were satisfied and interested in the results of the Action Strategy implemented by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in 2017-2021. Let’s remember how many significant measures have been determined and consistently implemented in the five priority areas of our country’s life on the basis of this program document, which was developed in cooperation with our people.

The second factor: President Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s New Uzbekistan Development Strategy is designed for 2022-2026, and within the framework of this programming document in 2022-2023 itself, the scope and scale of work performed in seven priority directions is commendable.

The third factor: at the eleventh meeting of the Movement of Entrepreneurs and Businessmen - the Liberal-Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, which was held as part of the election campaign, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the presidential candidate from this political party,

presented his election program to the voters.

All three strategic programs of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, are extremely popular because they were developed based on the suggestions of our compatriots and international partners.

The strategic programs of the President of Uzbekistan fully cover all spheres of the life of our state and society. At the same time, every person in our country will get favorable opportunities, certain reliefs, material and spiritual benefit from the implementation of measures in these programs, and in turn, every family and household will find prosperity, abundance, grace and blessings.

In conclusion, the results of this election, based on the free will, goals and dreams of our people, will serve to ensure the well-being and happiness of our people, guarantee the prosperity, peace and development of our country, and raise the prestige and image of our Motherland at the world level.

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